

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING SPEED-STRENGTH TRAINING IN SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING

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Annotation: The article discusses a systematic and structural approach to the development of movements aimed at increasing the speed and strength training of people involved in short-distance running.

Key words: athletics, mastery of technique, training process, accessibility, diversity.

Introduction. Track and field athletics is the kind of sport which unite exercises on walking, running, jumping and throwing as well as other kind of exercises which are consisted of these kinds [3, 5, 7]. In the learning programs of special higher educational establishments namely on faculties of physical education track and field athletics is the obligatory learning subject and this kind of sport takes the important place at overall training of specialists. During learning the students learn rational technique of track and field athletics' exercises to do moving activities as coordinated and precise as for direction, amplitude, force, rhythm that is students learn ability of control their activities and movements [1, 2]. The moving experience which are gained during lessons on track and field athletics positively effects on forming labour skills. The lessons will be more interesting and useful when students gain knowledge not only on theory and methodology of track and field athletics but also on adjacent subjects such as pedagogics, psychology, physiology, hygiene etcetera [4, 6].

During training process loads gradually risen; there are various difficulties which must be overcome. Doing lessons at adverse meteorological conditions,

competition with stronger opponents, adhering rules and sport ethics promote education of moral and strong-willed qualities of athlete such as patriotism, purposefulness, hard-working, diligence, resoluteness, boldness, self-possession, honesty etcetera [8, 9].

Comparative simplicity of lesson places creates conditions for application of lessons for improving health of students from early age. The value of track and field athletics' exercises is that during the lessons physical qualities are being developed such as force, quickness, endurance, flexibility, adroitness. Sports walking and long-term running makes active the action of various elements of organism. Running on short distances promotes developing quick and force abilities, running on mean and long distances promotes endurance, running with obstacles promotes adroitness, coordination of movements [10, 12]. Jumping exercises promote quickness, quick and force abilities; these exercises improve coordination of movements. The lessons on throwing promote development of force, quick and force abilities.

When determining the methodological approach to the study, we were guided by the need to use modern methodology in this work. The specific scientific problems that determine the concept of this work, its goals and objectives, as well as the choice of objects and research methods, were based on the provisions for teaching cyclic and acyclic exercises in athletics developed by domestic experts. We took into account specific pedagogical means and methods when preparing athletes specializing in short and middle distance running.

This method contributed to the creation of a correct idea and understanding of the theoretical foundations of the goal we are developing. The list of literary sources included works by Russian and foreign authors, as well as works on cyclic sports, works on the theory and methods of physical education. In order to obtain informative material and an in-depth, comprehensive study of the importance of means and methods of training athletes, pedagogical observations were carried out. The goal of training in athletics is to prepare the athlete for the selected types of sports exercises. An athlete must harmoniously combine spiritual wealth, moral

purity and physical perfection [13, 15]. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to strengthen health, improve harmonious development, master a system of knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of athletics, and master sportsmanship in selected types of athletics [14, 17, 18].

When working with different groups, these general guidelines must be specified and supplemented depending on the conditions, place and time of classes. Athletic training for an athlete includes different types of training, moral and volitional, theoretical, general and special physical, technical, tactical, organizational and methodological, and performance in competitions [16, 19]. The specific content of training for the main groups involved in athletics is revealed in programs for children's and youth sports schools and sports sections. The means of training an athlete include physical exercise, hygienic factors (regime, personal hygiene, massage) and the healing forces of nature [20].

Physical exercise is a specific means of sports training. These are specific movements, human actions, specially organized and performed to solve the problems of physical education.

Physical exercises as a means of sports training for an athlete can be divided into main, or sports (walking, running, jumping, throwing), and auxiliary. The latter, in turn, can be divided into two groups - general developmental and specially auxiliary. Depending on the tasks being solved, specially auxiliary exercises can be leading, guiding or corrective (to eliminate errors) and specially developmental (to develop special qualities). The classification of physical exercises depending on their purpose makes it possible to take into account specific working conditions (in particular, the sports specialization of those involved), does not assign exercises once and for all to one of the groups of this scheme, and at the same time facilitates orientation in a large number of sports training means. In each physical exercise, in each specific movement, the following aspects should be determined:

- a) starting position;
- b) moving parts of the body;

- c) direction of movement;
- d) amplitude;
- e) speed;
- f) the strength of muscle tension;
- g) coordination of movements;
- h) quantity or duration;
- i) frequency of movements.

The first three sides of movements allow us to determine which major muscle groups are involved in a given movement, and the remaining sides determine how these muscle groups work. When performing any physical exercise, you can highlight and strengthen one or another side of the movements. This human ability characterizes the level of development of individual motor properties. Exercises, during which one of the sides of the movement is strengthened, are called specially developing speed, strength, endurance, and the like. Concentration of trainees' attention on using the fullest possible range of movements is typical for flexibility exercises, emphasizing the speed and frequency of movements - for exercises that develop the quality of speed. A gradual increase in the force of resistance to movement and, in connection with this, an increase in nervous excitation and muscle tension is typical for strength exercises. Increasing the duration (or number) of movements is typical for exercises aimed at developing and improving endurance. When performing exercises in which large muscle groups are involved in the work, the working conditions of the muscles change dramatically; the requirements for their consistency, improvement, coordination of movements and dexterity are increasing.

In an athlete's daily routine, it is necessary to ensure alternation of work and rest, regularity of training sessions, timely nutrition, sleep, etc. Without following the correct regime, it is impossible to achieve high sports results. An athlete should sleep 8-9 hours and eat regularly. It is necessary to ensure that food is varied, high in calories and rich in vitamins. Smoking and drinking alcohol are prohibited. Every

morning, the athlete is required to do specialized exercises and warm-up and take a water procedure (shower, rubdown). It is advisable to regularly use massage and self-massage. A restorative massage after heavy exercise is especially useful. Sun rays (very moderate), air, water are used to improve health and harden.

Sports training methods are ways and means of communicating and consolidating the necessary knowledge, forming and improving motor skills, developing the abilities of those involved in sports and their moral and volitional qualities. It is important to take into account not only the unity, but also the differences in the means and methods used to solve the problems of sports training. A means is the specific content of a person's actions, and a method is a method of action in solving a problem. Means are indicated in response to the question "what to use?", and methods - in response to the question "how to use?"

The methods of training and education used in the process of sports training of track and field athletes are diverse. Their choice is determined by the tasks to be solved and specific working conditions - the composition of the students, time, place of classes and other circumstances.

In training athletes, the following groups of methods can be distinguished.

1. Methods of moral education: a) personal example of the trainer; b) organization of sports; d) motivation, encouragement; e) training (exercise); f) penalty, punishment.
2. Methods of teaching (mastering new material): a) teaching the technique of the exercise as a whole; c) word method (description, explanation, command); d) display, demonstration; e) leadership; f) direct assistance; g) independent work on assignment.
3. Methods for improving skills and developing qualities: a) repeated; b) variable; c) interval; d) competition.
4. Methods of load regulation: a) changing the frequency, duration and density of classes; b) change in the intensity of effort when performing movements; c) alternating tension of the main muscle groups "active rest".

5. Accounting methods: a) assessment of knowledge and quality of equipment in points; b) compliance with standards; c) participation in competitions; d) biometric measurements and functional tests; e) business characteristics of the athlete's personality.

Exercise as a means is a specific movement, action (or physical exercise), purposeful and specially organized to solve training problems.

Conclusions. From the perspective of a systemic-structural approach, perfect sports technique is considered as a specialized system of movements aimed at rationally organizing the interaction of internal and external forces with the aim of using them most fully and effectively to achieve high sports results. In this case, a system is understood as one whole, naturally uniting in a certain sequence heterogeneous components (elements), which are interconnected and interact with each other.

The main indicators for assessing sports technique for performing movements are efficiency, reliability, economy, simplicity and naturalness.

1. Efficiency and reliability are manifested in the maximum use of the athlete's physical abilities under any changes in internal and external environmental conditions.

2. An informative indicator of the effectiveness of a technique for performing an athletic exercise is the ratio of motor potential (an integral indicator of the level of development of physical qualities, the manifestation of which determines the solution of a motor task) to the achieved sports result.

3. Economy of movements in the economical expenditure of physical and mental strength, especially in exercises that require long-term performance of movements (medium, long and ultra-long distance running). Efficiency can be concluded based on energy costs when performing exercises.

4. Simplicity and naturalness of movements in all variants characterize perfect sports technique. This is due to the external ease of execution and lack of constraint.

It is also necessary to note the aesthetic perception of performing an exercise with perfect sports technique.

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